

ARTS

MANNERISM IN ITALIAN SCULPTURE

Sadikhova S.

*Doctor of philosophy in art-criticism
The senior lecturer of the chair "Descriptive art"
Nakhchivan State University, Azerbaijan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10226057>*

Abstract

The Mannerism trend in Italian sculpture was popular from about the 1520s to the 1590s. This movement was applied in many forms of visual and decorative art, and partly in architecture. Sculptors such as C.A. Montorsoli, B. Bandinelli, B. Cellini, B. Ammanati, C. Bologna were the brilliant representatives of Mannerism in this field. This movement was applied in many types of art, partly in architecture. At the beginning of XVII century, this direction became completely baroque.

Keywords: mannerism, sculpture, style, C.A. Montorsoli, B. Bandinelli, B. Cellini, B. Ammanati, C. Bologna

During the occupation and looting of Italy by the Spanish army in the XV and XVI centuries, an economic and social crisis occurred, the authority of the ruling church was undermined, the idea of a harmonious world order was violated, at this time the ideals of art changed, and the direction of mannerism began to manifest itself. This trend coincides with the last stage of the Renaissance [1, p. 253].

This direction in sculpture was popular from about the 1520s to the 1590s. The term mannerism is "mannerismo" - an Italian word that means "manner, style".

Seyyare Sadikhova elaborates the style of Mannerism in the types of art notes: "In the art of the Mannerists, the human image loses not only its heroic significance, but gradually loses its content and independent meaning, subjecting itself to conventionality and purely aristocratic ideals" [3, p.15].

Aspects such as deliberate deformation, neutrality of space, neglect of nature, diagonality of figures in stretched perspectives, violation of proportionality and symmetry are mentioned as the main features of the author's mannerism [3, p. 15].

This movement was applied in many types of art, partly in architecture [2].

The formation of the direction of mannerism in sculpture was also related to the city of Florence. Already in the 20s of XX century, anti-Renaissance tendencies appeared in Florentine sculpture and were manifested in the work of Giovanni Angelo Montorsoli (1507-1563). Pessimistic depression and mixed mood prevail in his works from the 20s and 30s. On the tombstone of Angelo Aretino, located in the church of San Pietro in Arezzo, he depicts the dead person with traces of decay and destruction, and in the portrait bust of Tomazzo Cavalcanti in the church of San Spirito in Florence, he distorts his face with wrinkles of horror and suffering. He clearly uses the grotesque. In the used reference, the concept of grotesque is interpreted as follows: "Grotesque is excessive expression, distortion, excessive hatred of the image chosen by the author" [4].

Montorsoli's youth works are characterized by the crisis of the traditions of Renaissance painting, by the

rejection of plastic integrity in the artistic solution of sculptures, and by attempts at naturalistic expression, which will later become the characteristic traditions of mannerist sculpture.

Montorsoli's work in the Medici chapel, while working as an assistant to Michelangelo in the early 1530s, was of great importance in shaping Montorsoli's work. From this time, the repetition of many compositional schemes of Michelangelo appears in the works of Montorsoli. Even the same one of Michelangelo's "Mourning" is reproduced in the church of San Mateo in Genoa. But he follows the path of a more organic assimilation of some aspects of his teacher's work, although the mood of depression and deep despair in his art is increasing. Apparently, this was the reason that forced the twenty-three-year-old artist to go to a monastery.

If Montorsoli belongs to the masters who acutely and painfully understood the tragic contradictions of Italian reality, his great contemporary Baccio Bandinelli (1488/93-1560) was closely connected with the Medici family from the first days (for this reason, during the revolt of 1527 he was obliged to flee) acts as the creator of the dominant movement in Florentine sculpture.

Bandinelli's work, first of all, testifies to the violation of the traditions of monumental sculpture, which is very characteristic of Mannerism. The fruitlessness of mannerism and ideological restrictions affect this type of sculpture with the greatest destructive force. Thus, Bandinelli's huge sculptural group "Heracles and Cacus", placed in the Signoria square in 1534 and claiming to compete with Michelangelo's "David", lacks both heroism and real monumentality: the sculptures are distinguished by natural roughness, unnatural tension of muscles. The figure of Heracles appears stiff and gaunt, the faces resemble grotesque mascarons, and the general silhouette of the group is extremely expressionless [5].

More unfortunate is the monument to the condottiere Giovanni delle Banda Nere (1540s), father of Cosimo I, in Piazza San Lorenzo. At the same time, from

the early 1540s, Bandinelli acted as the founder of the academic idealizing movement, which found direct analogies in the Mannerist painting of that time. Apathy and coldness grow in his art. The reliefs of the Florence Cathedral from 1553, the Adam and Eve statues in the National Museum of Florence can be cited as examples. At this time, he treats even tragic topics with complete indifference. For example, the scene in the "Mourning" statue in Santa Annunziata (1559) took on the appearance of an ordinary ritual. The plastic style that Bandinelli has developed over the years is a reflection of the principles of Renaissance sculpture. In order to emphasize the cold ideality of the images, Bandinelli tries to deliberately generalize the volumes, to achieve the maximum smoothness of the marble surface, which is his favorite material.

One of the bright representatives of Mannerist sculpture was Benvenuto Cellini (1500-1571). He was one of the most prominent personalities of his time as a sculptor, jeweler, art critic and talented writer. He was constantly in conflict between his palace tasteful creations and the surrounding society. This leaves an imprint on his work. On the one hand, Cellini acts as a representative of the decorative trend in mannerist sculpture, and on the other, he is the only Florentine master of the mid-16th century who is trying to return heroic significance to sculpture.

In the 1520-1530s, Cellini worked at the papal court, acting primarily as a jeweler and medalist, who brilliantly mastered the traditions of Renaissance small-form plastic art. After returning to Florence in 1545, Cellini finally devoted himself to sculpture.

However, the central place in Cellini's work is occupied by the problem of creating a heroic image, so alien to the Florentine mannerists of his time. The most remarkable work of Cellini, the bronze statue of Perseus (1545-1554).

The large statue of Perseus is one of the most outstanding and plastically perfect works of Italian monumental sculpture after Michelangelo. Cellini managed to create an image of a beautiful, proud triumphant, full of inner significance and noble restraint. He gives the pose and gestures of the hero, raising high the severed head of Medusa, calm confidence, inner strength and at the same time thoughtful concentration.

In the later period, Cellini, who lost popularity in court circles and devoted himself almost entirely to literary and theoretical works.

In the second half of XX century. Florentine sculpture acquires a purely decorative character. Thus, fountain and garden sculpture, as well as chamber sculpture intended for decorating small interiors, are receiving great development. The dominant sculpture in the second half of the 16th century was the courtly-aristocratic direction, the largest master of which was the already mentioned architect Bartolomeo Ammanati (1511-1592). A student of Bandinelli, Ammanati inherited from his teacher the desire for ideal generalization and

some abstractness in the interpretation of sculptural form.

The period of the most active creative activity of the Ammanati sculptor begins after his return to Florence in 1555. During these years, Ammanati strives for greater intimacy in his images and at the same time increasingly subordinates the human figure, its proportions, movements to the conventional mannerist canon and ornamental rhythm. The culmination of all Ammanati's searches of these years is a small bronze statue of Venus for the Studiolo Francesco I (1571), which in its most polished and perfect form embodies the cold and refined ideal of Florentine mannerism of the second half of XVI century.

The limiting influence of the abstract and conventional ideals of court art of this period is even more evident in the work of Giovanni da Bologna (1524-1608), a native of the Netherlands, who worked in Florence from 1553. This master, who completed the development of mannerist sculpture, combines the most diverse and contradictory trends in his work [5].

From Dutch art he inherited genre motifs (the Birdcatcher figurine) and the desire for naturalistic illusoryness, which was reflected in his famous sculptural images of birds and the decoration of the grottoes of the Villa Castello. His small models for fountain sculpture (Bathing Venus) are distinguished by the freedom of sculptural modeling and internal dynamism.

Giovanni da Bologna demonstrates his extraordinary talent by developing, following Cellini, the problem of conveying complex movement in a round sculpture that requires a circular walk. He provides a brilliant solution to this problem in the statue of Mercury, depicted in swift flight (1560s), and in the sculptural group "The Rape of the Sabine Woman" (1580-1583), which became a model for Baroque masters. Thus, by the end of XVI century, in the field of sculpture, the aesthetic ideals of Mannerism revealed their unviability. This result of the development of mannerism is natural; its representatives failed to pave new paths in art. At the beginning of XVII century, this direction became completely baroque.

References:

1. Под общей редакцией Ю.Д.Колпинского и Е.И.Ротенберга «Всеобщая история искусств», том 3., Москва-1962, 540 стр.
2. Под редакцией Нессельштрауса Ц.Г., История искусства зарубежных стран Москва-1982, 664 стр.
3. Sadikhova S. Mannerism in Italian art in XVI-XVII centuries. The Norwegian Journal of the Development of the International Science. No120, 2023.
4. Səyyarə Sadıxova. Xalq rəssamı Hüseynqulu Əliyevin sənət dünyası (albom-monoqrafiya). Naxçıvan: "Əcəmi" Nəşriyyat-Poliqrafiya Birliyi, 2019, 176 səh.
5. http://totalarch.ru/art_history/renaissance/italy/cinquecento/venice_art